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Avda. Juan de Herrera, 6-28040-MADRID

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ABSTRACTS BOOK

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ESCUELA TÉCNICA SUPERIOR DE EDIFICACIÓN

Avenida Juan de Herrera, 6. 28040 – Madrid

Tel. 91 336 75 95 Fax: 91 336 76 44

Organizador: Departamento de Tecnología de la Edificación de la ETSEM.

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CRAFT AND CONSTRUCTION. ARCHITECTURAL HERITAGE AND SUSTAINABLE INTERVENTION

¹M^a Paz Sáez-Pérez, ²Jorge A. Durán Suárez, ³Joao Castro Gomes

¹UGR, Buildings Constructions Department, Campus Fuentenueva, c/ Severo Ochoa, s/n, 18071, University of Granada, Spain, mpsaez@ugr.es

²UGR, Sculpture Department, Avenida de Andalucía, 27, 18014 University of Granada, Spain, giorgio@ugr.es

³UBI, Civil Engineering and Architecture Department, Marquês de Ávila e Bolama, 6201-001, University of Beira Interior, Covilhã, Portugal, jpcg@ubi.pt

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Abstract

Nowadays, architectural heritage is considered an essential part of the economy and tourism of many countries, which is why intervention, recovering and enhancing it is a key objective. Focused on the process of building rehabilitation, the objectives focus on valuing its identifying heritage features, with the respect for the original work, to adapt them to current needs, including new uses, ensuring that the intervention is carried out in the planned deadline, with the highest quality construction and ensuring that budget deviations are avoided.

A large part of the necessary actions require considering elements and processes that come from an artisanal action, defined as the elaboration of objects through the transformation of basic natural raw materials, through non-industrial production processes that involve simple machines and tools [1]. Currently, the situation of progressive disappearance of the artistic trades can endanger numerous interventions on the built heritage.

For this reason, the purpose of this research is to highlight the importance of crafts in the recovery of elements and heritage assets and how their intervention supposes an unavoidable action that also supposes the development of more sustainable actions [2, 3].

Faced with a changing environment such as the current one and globalization as an element present in the economy, traditional crafts have been systematically excluded, on the one hand due to the lack of definition as a productive sector, as is the case in Europe where in some states members only recognize traditional and artistic trades, with the fewest considering it to be a relatively broad part of the activity [4]. On the other hand, the distance that has been maintained between craftsmanship and technological progress, which today tends to disappear by including digital tools as a key element in advancing design processes and fundamentally reducing costs, which allows establish a model of resurgence of the competitiveness of artisanal producers [3,5].

Figure 1 shows a diagram of the involvement of crafts in the heritage intervention sector.

Figure 1: Heritage and handcraft (Authors' image)

The results obtained show very outstanding examples of handcrafted intervention as an unavoidable part of the architectural and construction process, which require the use of handmade processes, being the case of studies carried out in various investigations after the characterization of the materials used for its construction [6-9], or more recently in the interventions carried out in the Sagrada Familia (Barcelona, Spain) with the stonework, steel and glass trades, or Notre Dame (Paris, France), considering combining original materials recovered after the fire or in the case of wood treated in an artisanal way, guaranteeing the recovery of innumerable characteristic symbols of Chinese architectural culture.

The main conclusions confirm that the future and viability of the intervention and recovery of heritage architecture is based on three key elements: industrial production centers, technological innovation and craftsmanship.

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